

Multi-Objective Route Optimization via Dueling DQN for Teleoperated Driving

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Abstract—This paper presents a new approach to route optimization for teleoperated driving systems, addressing the multi-objective challenge of simultaneously minimizing travel distance, network latency, and maximizing available bandwidth. We model a real-world urban environment as a graph with stochastic network parameters and employ a Dueling Deep Q-Network (Dueling DQN) architecture, chosen for its ability to decouple state value and action advantage estimation, making it effective for routing problems requiring evaluation of both position quality and transition decisions.

Our approach achieves the highest combined performance score (1.3956), representing 3.4% and 4.3% improvements over Lowest Latency (1.3815) and Shortest Path (1.3380) algorithms respectively. This demonstrates effective multi-objective trade-off management: 56.9% KPI compliance (30ms latency, 20Mbps bandwidth) with minimal distance overhead (40 vs 30 spatial units). Single-objective approaches fail to balance requirements—Shortest Path achieves only 22.6% KPI compliance, while Highest Bandwidth produces impractically long routes (120 spatial units) despite 99.2% KPI rate.

Results demonstrate our Dueling DQN’s effectiveness in dynamically balancing competing objectives, providing intelligent adaptation to changing network conditions—a capability traditional single-objective optimization approaches cannot achieve.

Index Terms—Teleoperated Driving, Reinforcement Learning, Dueling DQN, Multi-Objective Optimization, Route Optimization, Digital Twin, 6G Networks

I. INTRODUCTION

Teleoperated driving serves as a critical bridge technology for autonomous vehicle systems. Effective teleoperation requires Ultra-Reliable Low-Latency Connectivity (URLLC) for real-time control signals and Enhanced Mobile Broadband (eMBB) for transmitting high-definition video feeds to the remote operator. These requirements create a multi-objective optimization problem where routes must balance physical travel distance with network performance metrics. The emergence of 6G network technologies offers unprecedented capabilities for teleoperated driving, but effectively utilizing these networks requires intelligent route planning strategies that consider both physical road constraints and dynamic network conditions.

In this paper, we propose a new multi-objective route optimization framework based on reinforcement learning (RL), specifically utilizing a Dueling Deep Q-Network (Dueling DQN) architecture. This approach is particularly well-suited for teleoperated driving applications due to the inherent dynamicity of telecommunications environments, where bandwidth and latency parameters change over time, where traditional static optimization methods struggle to address these

changes effectively. Furthermore, the multi-objective nature of teleoperated driving that requires simultaneously balancing physical distance constraints with network metrics, creates a complex optimization space that RL can navigate more efficiently.

Our framework simultaneously optimizes three critical objectives: minimizing physical travel distance, latency, and maximizing available bandwidth. We formulate this problem as a Markov Decision Process (MDP) where states represent the vehicle’s current position and network conditions, actions correspond to selecting the next road segment, transitions capture the stochastic nature of network parameters as the vehicle moves, and rewards are designed as a weighted combination of distance, bandwidth, and latency metrics. This MDP formulation enables our reinforcement learning approach to learn policies that adapt to changing network conditions while making appropriate trade-offs between competing objectives.

Our key contributions include:

- 1) A comprehensive system model that transforms real-world urban environments into a computational representation with time-varying network metrics for RL-based optimization.
- 2) A Dueling DQN architecture designed specifically for multi-objective route planning in teleoperated driving, featuring action masking to enforce graph connectivity constraints.
- 3) Integration with a digital twin framework that replicates the inter-dependencies between physical infrastructure and telecommunications networks
- 4) Extensive performance evaluation comparing our approach against classical routing algorithms (shortest path, lowest latency, and highest bandwidth)

This work represents a key contribution to the 6GTwin project [1], which aims to develop comprehensive digital twin solutions for 6G networks. Within this framework, our multi-objective route optimization serves as a functional model that enhances the capabilities of the Network Digital Twin (NDT)¹ architecture. By integrating network metrics with physical infrastructure modeling, our approach aligns with the project’s goal of creating intelligent, adaptive networking solutions

¹An NDT is a dynamic, bidirectional digital representation of a physical network. It integrates real-time data from network components-such as base stations, user devices, and core infrastructure-into a virtual environment.

that respond to the dynamic requirements of next-generation applications such as teleoperated driving.

The remainder of this paper is organized as follows: Section II examines related work; Section III details our methodology for transforming urban environments into graph-based models; Section IV explains our proposed solution; Section V provides performance evaluation, and Section VII concludes with future research directions.

II. RELATED WORK

The integration of network metrics into traffic routing represents a complex multi-objective optimization problem spanning several research domains. Teleoperated driving has gained significant attention as a robust fallback solution for automated vehicles. Zhang et al. [2] proposed a Predicted Trajectory Guidance Control framework compensating for communication delays, while Majstorović et al. [3] presented a dynamic collaborative path planning approach for remote assistance of automated vehicles. Schippers et al. [4] investigated performance requirements for predictive QoS in teleoperated driving applications, proposing Radio Environmental Maps for data rate prediction. Route optimization started off as a problem with a single objective such as minimizing distance or travel time. Regragui and Moussa [5] proposed a real-time path planning strategy addressing communication overhead in vehicular networks. Classical path planning techniques include cell decomposition methods employing graph-based algorithms like Dijkstra and A* [6]. Wang et al. [7] proposed a dynamic fuzzy routing approach addressing latency and bandwidth guarantees simultaneously in Software-Defined Networks, highlighting the complex relationship between competing metrics.

Recently, Reinforcement learning has emerged as a powerful approach for solving complex routing problems. The Dueling Deep Q-Network architecture [8] separates state value and advantage estimation, enabling more efficient policy evaluation in complex decision-making domains. Zhang et al. [9] explored applying reinforcement learning to robot path planning by modeling it as a Markov decision process with Q-learning algorithms, while Arulkumaran et al. [10] provided a comprehensive survey of deep reinforcement learning applications. Researchers have identified challenges in applying RL to path planning, including high computational resource consumption and reduced convergence rates with increased state spaces [11], [12]. Jaramillo-Martínez et al. [13] demonstrated the importance of careful reward function engineering in balancing multiple objectives.

Digital twin technology has gained traction for modeling the dynamic relationship between physical infrastructure and network performance [4], though its integration with route optimization algorithms for next-generation networks remains an open research area.

While existing literature addresses various aspects of teleoperated driving, multi-objective optimization, and reinforcement learning for routing problems, there remains a significant gap in integrating these domains to create a comprehensive

solution that balances physical and network-related objectives. Our work advances the state of the art by developing a system model that transforms real-world urban environments into a computational representation suitable for reinforcement learning; proposing a Dueling DQN architecture specifically designed for multi-objective route planning; integrating a digital twin framework that simulates the interdependencies between physical and network infrastructure; and providing extensive performance evaluation against classical routing algorithms. In contrast to previous work, our approach considers both the physical aspects of route planning and the network requirements as equally important optimization objectives, creating a more holistic solution for connected vehicle applications.

III. METHODOLOGY

This section presents our system model for multi-objective route optimization in teleoperated driving. We transform a real-world urban environment into a computational representation suitable for reinforcement learning, integrating network metrics essential for teleoperation. Studies by Lucas-Estan et al. [14] and network characteristics documented in [15], show the latency ranging from 10ms to 50ms and bandwidth from 10Mbps to 100Mbps. These parameters are incorporated into our model using 5G base station locations to create a realistic representation of network conditions across the urban environment.

A. Physical Environment Description

We model the urban environment as a directed graph $G = (V, E)$ where intersections form nodes and road segments form edges, chosen because this representation naturally discretizes the continuous routing problem into a finite state-action space suitable for reinforcement learning. Graph-based modeling enables efficient action masking through connectivity constraints and provides computational tractability for multi-objective optimization. We selected Nevers, France as our test environment, converting its road network from OpenStreetMap data [16].

To manage computational complexity while maintaining representational fidelity, we applied clustering to reduce the original 329 nodes and 593 edges to 50 nodes and 228 edges, preserving the fundamental optimization challenges. The clustering transformation was designed to ensure appropriate connectivity for our reinforcement learning method, targeting an average node degree of 4.0 to create a Manhattan-like grid structure. For each edge in this clustered graph, we preserved the network metrics by identifying and mapping the closest corresponding edge from the original network, thereby maintaining realistic network characteristics despite the structural simplification.

We incorporated network metrics into our graph by leveraging 5G base station deployment data from the OpenCellID dataset [17]. Each edge in our model includes three key attributes:

- 1) **Physical distance** ($d(e)$): The geometric length of each road segment measured in meters.
- 2) **Expected latency** ($l(e, \tau)$): The network latency at time τ , modeled using a normal distribution with parameters derived from proximity to the nearest 5G base station. Values range from 10ms to 50ms [15].
- 3) **Anticipated bandwidth** ($b(e, \tau)$): The available bandwidth at time τ , modeled similarly using a normal distribution with values between 10Mbps and 100Mbps [15].

For both latency and bandwidth, we generated values following normal distributions over a 1800-second time horizon, providing a more realistic representation of network performance variability than deterministic values. Given Nevers' characteristics as a small urban area with relatively low traffic density, we assumed that congestion effects would be minimal compared to network-induced latency variations.

Based on established teleoperation standards, we defined the Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) for the minimum viable conditions as: Latency ≤ 30 ms, bandwidth ≥ 20 Mbps [14], [15].

B. Integration with 6GTwin project

The multi-objective route optimization framework proposed in this paper is designed as a functional component within the broader 6GTwin Network Digital Twin (NDT) architecture. Figure 1 illustrates the comprehensive NDT architecture developed for the 6GTwin project [1].

Fig. 1. 6GTwin Network Digital Twin Architecture. Our multi-objective route optimization framework is positioned as a functional model within this architecture, leveraging data from both physical and network layers to provide optimized routing for teleoperated vehicles.

C. Problem Formulation

Building upon the graph-based environment model, we formalize the multi-objective route optimization as finding a path $P = (v_1, v_2, \dots, v_n)$ through the directed graph G that optimally balances three competing objectives while respecting the graph's connectivity constraints and operational requirements: $L(P, \tau) \leq 30$ ms and $B(P, \tau) \geq 20$ Mbps.

- 1) **Minimize Total Distance:**

$$\min D(P) = \sum_{e \in P} d(e) \quad (1)$$

- 2) **Minimize End-to-End Latency:**

$$\min L(P, \tau) = \sum_{e \in P} l(e, \tau) \quad (2)$$

- 3) **Maximize Minimum Bandwidth:**

$$\max B(P, \tau) = \min\{b(e, \tau)\} \text{ for all } e \in P \quad (3)$$

This multi-objective nature, combined with stochastic network metrics, makes the problem particularly suitable for reinforcement learning approaches that can adapt to dynamic conditions while balancing competing objectives.

IV. EXPERIMENTAL SETUP

This section outlines our reinforcement learning approach to multi-objective route optimization for teleoperated driving. We employ a DDQN architecture designed to balance the competing objectives of distance minimization, latency reduction, and bandwidth maximization.

A. Markov Decision Process and State-Reward Formulation

To formalize our multi-objective route optimization problem, we represent it as an MDP with a comprehensive state representation and carefully balanced reward function:

1) **MDP Framework:** The optimal route selection for teleoperated driving is modeled as MDP $M = (S, A, R)$, illustrated in Figure 2. The state space S encodes vehicle position, destination, network conditions, and path metrics (14 dimensions total). The action space A consists of selecting adjacent nodes with masking to prevent invalid moves.

Fig. 2. MDP formulation with concrete routing example showing state transitions, actions, and multi-objective rewards in teleoperated driving scenario.

The multi-objective reward function balances competing objectives:

$$R(s, a) = w_d \cdot R_d(s, a) + w_b \cdot R_b(s, a) + w_l \cdot R_l(s, a) \quad (4)$$

where $R_d = -d(e)/d_{max}$, $R_b = (b(e, \tau) - b_{min})/(b_{max} - b_{min})$, and $R_l = -l(e, \tau)/l_{max}$ represent normalized distance, bandwidth, and latency components. Optimal weights $w_d = 0.5$, $w_b = w_l = 0.25$ prioritize distance while balancing network metrics, with additional bonuses/penalties

for target achievement (+10.0), loop prevention (-5.0), and invalid actions (-10.0).

The agent learns policy π^* maximizing expected cumulative reward through Dueling DQN’s action-value function $Q(s, a)$, converging toward optimal multi-objective solutions via experience replay.

B. Dueling DQN Framework

The core of our approach is a specialized Dueling DQN architecture that decouples state value and action advantage estimation through two parallel streams, as illustrated in Figure 3. This separation allows the network to evaluate state value $V(s)$ independently from action advantages $A(s,a)$, making it particularly effective for routing problems where both position quality and transition decisions must be considered.

Fig. 3. Dueling DQN algorithm flowchart showing dual-stream architecture and action selection process with exploration-exploitation balance.

The architecture combines shared feature extraction with parallel value and advantage streams, aggregated as $Q(s,a) = V(s) + (A(s,a) - \text{mean}(A(s,a)))$. Our implementation incorporates action masking for graph connectivity constraints, preventing invalid moves to non-adjacent or previously visited nodes during both training and inference.

Training employed 5,000 episodes with random source-destination pairs using key hyperparameters: replay buffer (20,000 transitions), batch size (128), target network updates every 100 steps, discount factor =0.99, -greedy exploration (1.0→0.01, decay 0.9991), Adam optimizer (1e-4), and Huber loss. This regimen enabled effective learning of routing policies balancing distance, bandwidth, and latency optimization.

V. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

This section focuses on the performance evaluation of our Dueling DQN approach compared to classical routing algorithms.

A. Evaluation Framework

We evaluated our approach against three classical routing algorithms: Shortest Path (distance optimization), Lowest Latency, and Highest Bandwidth. The assessment used 2,500 random scenarios with key metrics including success rate, path length, distance, bandwidth, latency, and KPI respect rate (paths meeting minimum viable thresholds of $\leq 30ms$ latency and $\geq 20Mbps$ bandwidth).

B. Training Overview

Our agent was trained for 5,000 episodes on the Nevers city graph with random source-destination pairs. Figure 4 shows the training progression, with rapid improvement during the initial 500 episodes followed by stabilization. The success rate reached nearly 100% after a few hundred episodes.

Fig. 4. Training metrics: (top-left) rewards with moving average, (top-right) losses, (bottom-left) evaluation rewards, (bottom-right) success rates.

Path quality metrics (Figure 5) show significant improvements, with path length decreasing from approximately 30 to 4-5 nodes, distance reducing from over 400 to about 50 units, bandwidth increasing to near 60, and latency decreasing from over 600 to under 100.

Fig. 5. Path quality metrics: length (top-left), distance (top-right), bandwidth (bottom-left), latency (bottom-right).

C. Comparative Performance Analysis

The KPI respect rate is a critical metric for teleoperated driving applications, measuring the percentage of generated paths that simultaneously satisfy both minimum bandwidth (20 Mbps) and maximum latency (30 ms) requirements. Figure 6 shows that our RL agent achieved a 56.9% KPI respect rate, significantly outperforming the Shortest Path algorithm (22.6%) and performing comparably to the Lowest Latency algorithm (50.2%). The Highest Bandwidth algorithm achieved 99.2% but at the cost of significantly longer routes.

Fig. 6. KPI respect rate comparison (latency ≤ 50ms, bandwidth ≥ 15Mbps).

To better evaluate the multi-dimensional performance of each algorithm, We developed a unified metric combining KPI satisfaction and route efficiency to compare different routing approaches. This metric provides a holistic view of each algorithm’s ability to simultaneously satisfy telecommunications requirements while maintaining route efficiency. Figure 7 presents this combined performance analysis, where higher values indicate better overall performance across both dimensions, calculated as: Figure 7 presents this combined performance analysis, where higher values indicate better overall performance across both dimensions, calculated as follows:

$$\text{norm_inv_dist} = \frac{1/\text{avg_dist}}{\max(1/\text{dist_all})} \quad (5)$$

$$\text{combined_score} = \text{norm_kpi_rate} + \text{norm_inv_dist} \quad (6)$$

Our RL agent achieves the highest combined score (1.3956), demonstrating superior balance between network performance and route efficiency. The Lowest Latency algorithm follows closely (1.3815), while the Shortest Path algorithm (1.3380) performs well primarily due to its distance optimization. Most notably, the Highest Bandwidth algorithm scores lowest (0.9448) despite its excellent KPI respect rate, as its route inefficiency significantly impacts its practical utility for teleoperated driving applications.

D. Key Findings

Our analysis revealed four critical insights:

Fig. 7. Combined performance metric (normalized KPI respect rate + normalized inverse distance) demonstrating overall routing effectiveness across multiple objectives.

Fig. 8. Distance vs. KPI respect rate analysis showing algorithm positioning in the optimization space. The green area represents the ideal region.

- Balanced Distance:** While Shortest Path achieved the lowest average Euclidean distance (30 spatial units within our normalized graph representation), our agent generated paths with only marginal increases (40 units) while significantly improving network performance. These spatial units correspond to the relative distances between intersections in our clustered graph representation of Nevers.

- Effective Trade-offs:** The RL agent achieved competitive bandwidth performance while reducing path distance by approximately 67% compared to the Highest Bandwidth algorithm’s paths (120 units).

- Adaptive Capability:** The RL agent demonstrated particularly strong performance in scenarios with high network variability, where static algorithms often failed to adapt.

Our approach achieved the second best KPI respect rate after the specialized Highest Bandwidth algorithm while significantly outperforming it in distance optimization, demonstrating the effectiveness of reinforcement learning for multi-objective optimization in complex, dynamic environments.

VI. LIMITATIONS AND FUTURE WORK

Our proposed framework operates under several key limitations that must be acknowledged for practical deployment. The primary limitation lies in our network parameter generation methodology, where latency and bandwidth values are synthetically generated using normal distributions rather than utilizing real-time network measurements. This synthetic approach may not fully capture the complex temporal patterns present in actual network deployments. Additionally, deployment feasibility presents challenges regarding real-time integration of dynamic network data, as our system assumes instantaneous availability of network metrics across the entire road network, which would require continuous data feeds from network infrastructure providers in practice.

Future work will focus on incorporating empirical network measurements from actual 5G/6G deployments to validate our approach under real network conditions. We plan to extend our framework to multi-agent reinforcement learning where multiple teleoperated vehicles share real-time network performance data, investigate dynamic infrastructure augmentation such as aerial base stations, and address realistic traffic conditions including congestion patterns. These developments will enable practical deployment of intelligent routing systems for next-generation teleoperated driving applications.

VII. CONCLUSION

This research introduces a comprehensive multi-objective route optimization framework for teleoperated driving, demonstrating the effectiveness of reinforcement learning in balancing competing objectives of distance minimization, latency reduction, and bandwidth maximization. Our Dueling DQN architecture achieved the highest combined performance score (1.3956), representing 3.4% and 4.3% improvements over Lowest Latency (1.3815) and Shortest Path (1.3380) algorithms respectively, while maintaining effective multi-objective trade-off management with 56.9% KPI compliance and minimal distance overhead. The key insight revealed by our work is that maximizing a single metric leads to impractical routing solutions, while our reinforcement learning approach provides balanced routing strategies that adapt to dynamic network conditions. These findings establish a robust foundation for intelligent routing in teleoperated driving systems, opening new avenues for research in next-generation vehicular networks.

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